

THE CONCEPT AND ESSENCE OF THE DIVIDEND POLICY. FACTORS INFLUENCING THE DIVIDEND POLICY

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Abstract: The article reveals the concept and essence of the dividend and the dividend policy, as well as the factors influencing the dividend policy, and presents the existing theories of the dividend policy. A classification of the factors of the dividend policy into groups is proposed: economic, institutional and legal, social, and contractual.

Keywords: dividend policy, joint-stock company, dividend, essence, factors, profit.

Introduction. Profit is the main goal of any commercial organization. In the event of a successful end to the financial year, the company faces a dilemma: to direct the profit received for reinvestment in order to develop the organization or to encourage the owners of the company in the form of dividend payments. The question of the essence of the concepts of "dividend" and "dividend policy" is debatable. For example, V. V. Kovalev defines a dividend as "cash income of shareholders" [1, p. 123]. Galanov defines a dividend as income that a shareholder can acquire at the expense of a share of the net profit of a joint-stock company distributed among the shareholders in the form of a fixed part of their nominal value, i.e., the shareholder's right to participate in the profit is exercised with the help of a dividend [2, p.52]. Therefore, the concept of "dividend" can be defined as a part of the net profit of a joint-stock company after tax, which is paid to shareholders. The

concept of a dividend in Russia is defined by both the Civil and Tax Codes of the Russian Federation, but in the tax sense, its meaning is much broader. In accordance with the Civil Code, a dividend is recognized as the income received by a shareholder from a joint-stock company when distributing profits on shares owned by a shareholder in proportion to the shareholders' shares in the authorized capital of this company [3, Article 102]. In other words, dividends are paid only by joint-stock companies. From the point of view of taxation, a dividend is any income received by a shareholder from an organization when distributing the profit remaining after tax on the shares owned by the shareholder in proportion to the shareholders' shares in the authorized capital of this organization, i.e. any income received by a shareholder (participant) from the organization is recognized [4, Article 43]. Questions about how important the dividend policy is in the activities of a joint-stock company, whether it is necessary to pay dividends, whether the payment of dividends and their stability affects its market value (i.e., whether it is necessary to pay dividends). on the welfare of shareholders) are also debatable. Depending on the answers to these questions, the following basic theories of dividend policy are distinguished: the theory of the significance of dividend policy, the theory of the irrelevance of dividends, the theory of tax differentiation, the theory of dividend signaling, the theory of clientele [5, p.362]. Thus, the essence of the dividend policy is to choose the optimal ratio between the share of profit diverted from turnover and paid in the form of dividends, and the share directed to the expansion of the business. The following groups of factors influencing the company's dividend policy can be distinguished [5, p. 369]. First, the economic factors that characterize the firm's own investment opportunities include: - the need to use a favorable market environment to implement investment programs with a

high level of efficiency; - the availability of financial reserves formed in the previous period; - the stage of the organization's life cycle (in the early stages, it is forced to direct more funds to its development, limiting the payment of dividends). Characteristics of the possibility of attracting financial resources from alternative sources: - the financial condition and level of creditworthiness of the organization, which determine the degree of confidence in it of investors; - the weighted average cost of raising additional capital through the issue of shares and bonds, obtaining bank loans; - costs associated with the issue and placement of securities. Limiting factors: - the level of taxation of the company's property and dividends; - capital structure (the ratio of the corporation's debt obligations to its share capital), which reflects the coefficient of financial activity and characterizes the degree of dependence of the company on borrowed sources of financing; - the achieved effect of financial leverage (leverage), which allows manipulating the capital structure to influence the level of profitability of the company's assets, and therefore the market price of its shares; – the actual amount of profit received. Macro-economic: - the state of the commodity market in which the company operates (for example, during the recovery of market conditions, the efficiency of profit capitalization increases significantly); - inflation, high rates of which form the propensity of shareholders to receive dividends in cash, and the company's management to delay their payments (the latter is mainly due to the growth of the organization's need for cash). Other factors: - the need to pay off loans (is more important than increasing the level of dividends paid); – the level of dividend payments from competitors; - the risk of losing control over the management of the company (a low level of dividends can lead to a drop in the market value of the company's shares and their mass sale by the owners, which increases the risk of its capture). Secondly, a group of social factors:

The needs of owners regarding the dividend rate that maximizes their well-being (if most of the shares are concentrated in the hands of minority shareholders and / or institutional investors, then the most likely orientation is to pay high dividends; if the majority shareholders prevail, then there will be a refusal of significant dividends in favor of reinvesting profits). The opinion of senior managers about the strength of their position in the corporation (if a takeover is threatened, they can put their group interests above the interests of other owners and reduce its investment attractiveness without distributing dividends). Third, a group of institutional and legal factors: The restriction of the organization's ability to declare and pay dividends (the company is not entitled to do this if the authorized capital is not fully paid, the shares that it is obliged to buy back are repurchased, certain signs of bankruptcy are identified in the legislation, or these signs may appear as a result of the payment of dividends, the value of its net assets is less than the amount of the authorized capital and the reserve fund, or will become less than this value as a result of the payment of dividends). Requirements for the sources of dividend payments (in some countries, dividends can be paid only from profit; in others-from profit and investment income). Requirements for the form of dividend payments (dividends can be paid in cash, and in cases stipulated by the company's charter — in shares, bonds, goods). The sequence of dividend events (the date of the announcement and publication in the press by the Board of Directors of the payment of dividends, their size, terms of payment and payment). Fourth, a group of contractual factors that include the requirements of bilateral agreements concluded by the corporation and unilateral obligations that it has imposed on itself: A limit on dividend payments when receiving a loan (in order to provide debt service guarantees, the borrower enters into an agreement that specifies either a limit below which the amount of

retained earnings cannot fall, or a certain value of financial coefficients, until which dividend payments are not made). In Russia, this practice is not yet widespread, but there is a need to form a reserve capital of at least 5 % of the authorized capital, and to assign the board of directors the right to limit the amount of dividends paid in excess of the specified amount, which the management can use when obtaining long-term loans. Ensuring that the company's shares meet the criteria for admission to trading on major stock exchanges (for example, the absence of a reduction in dividend payments for a long time). The dividend policy, as well as the management of the company's capital structure, significantly affects the change in the total wealth of the participants of the joint-stock company. When deciding on the distribution of the company's profits between dividend payments and reinvestment, it is very important to take into account the possible reaction of the securities market, since the dividend policy has a significant impact on the company's share price, which serves as the main information for the investor about the effectiveness of its activities. Therefore, the model of the dividend policy should be built with reference to the share price, the value of enterprises. At the same time, the share price is affected not only by the company's profit as such and the amount of dividends paid, but also by such factors as its financial stability, popularity, the state of business activity in the country, the number of competitors, the level of inflation, legislative and tax changes, the effectiveness of the securities market, etc. With a significant increase in the market quotations of shares, there may come a point after which the demand for them begins to fall due to the high price. In this case, they resort to splitting the shares, the number of which in circulation increases. As a result, earnings and dividends per share, as well as its price, decrease, and demand for them

increases again. The assessment of these factors allows us to make a choice in favor of a certain type of dividend policy for the nearest period.

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